

EROSION BEHAVIOUR OF ALUMINIUM ALLOY MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The utilisation of aluminium matrix composites for components on production scale requires a strict knowledge on the behaviour of the materials in all conditions. In many process industry and power generation applications erosion and corrosion plays an important role on the life time of the component.

In this research the erosion resistance of hot extruded and upsetted powder metallurgical AA6061/SiCp and AA6061/Al₂O₃p and cast AlSiMg/SiCp composites is studied. Erosion testing is carried out in a fluidised bed erosion-corrosion rig at 100 and 150 °C temperatures. The apparatus employs counter-rotating rotors bearing tubular samples immersed in a fluidised bed of abrasive alumina particles. The effect of reinforcement material, size and content and heat treatment on the erosion properties are presented and the results are compared to those of corresponding unreinforced alloys. The surfaces of the eroded samples are analysed with SEM to study the material wastage mechanisms.

The results show that the volume loss and the erosion rate of the wrought PM materials are smaller as compared to that of the cast materials. The reinforcement addition and the variation of the reinforcement size do not affect on the erosion resistance of the wrought PM composites.

Keywords: Metal matrix composites, aluminium alloys, particulate reinforcement, particle erosion, fluidised bed erosion testing

1. INTRODUCTION

The addition of ceramic particulates into metal alloys has been shown to improve the wear resistance, strength and elastic modulus of these materials. However, the knowledge of erosion behaviour of these materials is very limited and only few papers have been published in this field [1-3].

The erosion of materials is not completely understood and a lot of theoretical models are developed concerning the mechanisms occurring in the process. Evidently the ductility and

hardness of the eroded material plays an important role together with the eroding media [4]. In the case of composites the mechanisms are even more complicated because the material consists of a ductile metal matrix and hard ceramic particulates. Also the bonding between the reinforcement and the matrix alloy influences greatly the material removal process.

The erosion by solid particle impact can cause the material removal by several mechanisms depending of the eroded material, surrounding conditions and the shape of erosion particles. The most common phenomena are cutting, gouging, tearing and ploughing [2].

In the present work the solid erosion resistance of hot extruded and upseted powder metallurgical AA6061/SiCp, AA6061/Al₂O₃p and cast AlSiMg/SiCp composites is studied in a fluidised bed erosion-corrosion rig at the temperatures of 100 °C and 150 °C. The effect of reinforcement material, size and content and heat treatment on the erosion properties are presented and the results are compared to those of corresponding unreinforced alloys.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1. Materials

The aluminium powder used for making the aluminium composites was a nitrogen-atomised alloy AA6061 (Al-1.0Mg-0.6-Si-0.25Cu-0.2Cr) having an average particle size of 28 µm (Coulter counter). As reinforcement, silicon carbide particulates with average particle sizes of 5, 13 or 29 µm (grades F1000, F500 of F320 respectively) and aluminium oxide particulates (Al₂O₃p) with an average particle size of 13 µm (grade F 500) were used.

The cast aluminium composites were manufactured by sand casting from commercial SiCp reinforced cast aluminium composite alloys F3S.10S (Al - 9Si - 0.6Mg - 10 vol. % SiCp (9 µm)) and F3S.20S (Al - 9Si - 0.6Mg - 20 vol. % SiCp (13 µm)). The reference alloy was a gravity die cast unreinforced primary alloy A356 (Al - 7Si - 0.4Mg).

2.2. Manufacturing of samples

The aluminium powder and the reinforcement particulates (10, 20 or 30 vol. %) were mixed in a Turbula shaking mixer. The mixed powder was encapsulated in an aluminium capsule (ø 70 x 70 mm) and vacuum degassed for 4 hours to about 10-4 mbar pressure while being heated to the extrusion temperature (540 °C). After degassing, the evacuation tube was sealed and the powder extruded into a bar.

All the extrusions were performed at a ram speed of 1 mm/s through a conical die, the die angle being 120°. The extrusion ratio was 17:1 and the diameter of the bars produced 18 mm. The extruded bars were cut to 35 mm long pieces and upseted for better describing the final material in any forged composite component. In upsetting the temperature was 400 °C and the reduction in height 49 %.

Aluminium composite ingots were dried thoroughly by preheating to at least 260 °C for about two hours or more before charging the melting furnace. Ingots were melted and held in the electric resistance furnace (max. 30 kg Al) under argon gas. An inert atmosphere was used during the total melting cycle, from ingot charging to molten bath, to prevent hydrogen and oxide pick-up.

The composite melts were mechanically and manually stirred in order to keep SiC particles in suspension and to prevent particles settling down on the bottom of the crucible. During stirring, excessive turbulence and breaking-up of the oxide skin on the melt furnace was avoided as far as possible. All hand stirring tools, skimmers and hand ladles were well coated, dried and heated before being placed in the melt.

The composite bars (Ø 22 mm) were cast in sodium silicate-bonded cylindrical sand moulds. The pouring temperature of the melt was 780 °C. The reference primary aluminium alloy A 356 was gravity die cast in a colloidal graphite-coated step plate mould. The pouring temperature of the

melt was 725 °C and the gravity die temperature 260 °C. The 18 mm thick step plate was used for erosion tests.

The erosion test samples were machined and ground from the wrought and cast pieces. After machining some of the pieces were heat-treated to T6 temper according to the following instructions:

AA6061 and AA6061 matrix composites:	Solution anneal for 1h at 530 °C, water quench, age for 8hrs at 175 °C
F3S.10S and F3S.20S:	Solutionized for 8 hrs at 538 oC Water quenched, aged for 5 hrs at 154 oC.
A356:	Solutionized for 8 hrs at 540 oC water quenched, aged for 16 hrs at room temperature, aged for 8 hrs at 160 oC.

2.3. Erosion testing

For erosion testing an equipment built into a commercial fluidised bed heat treatment furnace was used [5]. The furnace chamber of 300 mm in diameter and 600 mm deep is heated electrically from the outside. The heat is transferred from the chamber wall to the fluidised bed. Bed temperatures ranging from 100 °C up to 1000 °C are attainable. Pressurised air or other suitable gas may be used as fluidisation media.

The test rig was build only with minor modifications according to the standard model described by Entwisle, Hutchings and Little [6]. The test rig consists of four horizontal stainless steel rotor arms rotating to opposite directions by two concentric vertical axles in the fluidised bed. Bed movement with rig is thus avoided. Axles are belt driven and powered with two 1 kW electrical motors. When 80 Mesh alumina particles are used as bed material, a rotation speed of 250 r/min can be maintained. The rotation speed of each axle is measured and checked manually. From the materials to be tested cylindrical or tubular specimens are prepared and put onto the rotor arms. Omitting the random motion of the bed, particle impact velocities in the range of 1 m/s to 3 m/s are attainable at the rotation speed of 250 r/min. In these tests the material wastage was measured as a specimen weight loss, which is practical for short cylindrical specimens.

Specimens were washed with acetone, dried and weighted to 0.1 mg. Interrupted erosion tests lasting totally 100 h were conducted at the temperatures of 100 °C and 150 °C. At each test 8 specimens were simultaneously in a upper and a lower rotor arm. Further details of the testing programme are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Erosion corrosion test conditions.

Bed material	80 Mesh (170 µm) Al ₂ O ₃ particles
Bed density	2 kg dm ⁻³
Air rate	12-14 m ³ h ⁻¹
Rotation speed	250 r min ⁻¹
Temperatures	100 ±10 °C and 150 ±10 °C
Test duration	100 h, intermittent with weighing of specimens after 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 h
Specimens	Length 15 mm, outer diameter 20 mm
Velocity range	1.0 - 2.0 ms ⁻¹
Rotating distance	367 - 724 km

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The volume loss in erosion tests is presented in Fig. 1 as a function of the exposure time. The volume loss of the hot extruded powder metallurgical materials is clearly smaller as compared to those of the cast materials. In wrought alloys the effect of the reinforcement addition on the volume loss was negligible.

In the beginning of the test the erosion is typically faster than at longer erosion times and a steady state is achieved after about 40-60h of testing. It is possible that variations in the surface finish of the samples as well as the loose matrix alloy layer that has smeared on the surface during the machining of some of the samples may have led in differences in the initial erosion rate in the beginning of the test. Rough surface of the sample may result in a higher erosion rate in the beginning of the test than a smooth and sound surface.

Figure 1. The volume loss of the cast and wrought materials as a function of the erosion time at the temperature of 100 °C and 150 °C for the particle impact velocity of 2.0 m/s.

The results calculated from the steady state show that the erosion rate of the PM materials was smaller than that of the cast materials (Fig. 2). The addition of reinforcements did not seem to influence the erosion rate of the wrought alloys within the particle velocity range studied. Also the variation of the silicon carbide particulate size had no marked effect on the erosion rate. However, in the case of the Al₂O₃p-reinforced alloys the volume loss and the erosion rate were slightly smaller as compared to those of the SiCp-reinforced alloys. Of the cast alloys the T6-treated 20 vol.%SiCp containing alloy had a smaller volume loss and wear rate as compared to those of the as-cast 10 vol.%SiCp containing alloy.

An increase in the exposure temperature from 100 °C to 150 °C decreased the erosion rate of the wrought materials slightly. The reason for this may be an easier oxide layer formation or a formation of a more plastic protective oxide layer on the surface of the samples as the exposure temperature is increased. With higher reinforcement contents the difference becomes insignificant.

SEM research revealed that the surface of the test samples was partly deeply scratched in the machining and the reinforcements were covered with the matrix alloy. Both in cast and PM alloys and composites the erosion was strongest at the impact angle of 45° and very small on the surface perpendicular to the impact direction (Fig. 3 and 4). The material loss was greater for the cast materials. The erosion revealed the reinforcement particles which seems to be well bonded to the matrix and unaffected by the impacts of the erodents. The matrix material had deformed plastically in the direction of the erodent flow.

Figure 2. The erosion rate of the cast and the hot extruded PM alloys as a function of the reinforcement content at the temperatures of 100 °C and 150 °C for the particle impact velocity of 2.0 m/s.

The reasons for the erosion behaviour of composites can be a consequence of a number of things. The weak erosion of the sample surface perpendicular to the impact direction may result from the high ductility of the matrix material. The erosion of ductile materials is usually small at large impact angles while that of hard and brittle ones increases with the impact angle. Erosion gets stronger towards 45° impact angle probably because in that direction the erodents are more able to cut matrix alloy and remove the material.

Wrought composites were more erosion resistant than the cast materials evidently owing to their better ductility which promotes the material to resist the cutting action of the erodent particles. The addition of reinforcements decreased the ductility of the materials resulting in more effective cutting action of the erodent particles as suggested in reference [2]. However, the reinforcement also increased the hardness of the materials and so their resistance to the penetration of erodents was improved [2]. The interaction of these phenomena caused that the erosion resistance of the wrought PM composites was almost same as that of corresponding unreinforced alloy in the present conditions.

A356-T6 / 90°

a)

A356-T6 / 45°

b)

F3S.20S-T6 / 90°

c)

F3S.20S-T6 / 45°

d)

Figure 3. SEM micrographs of A356-T6 (a and b) and F3S.20S-T6 (c and d) samples after the 100 h erosion tests at 100 °C on the surfaces with impact angles of 90° (a and c) and 45° (b and d). The impact velocity was 1.4 ms⁻¹ for A356-T6 samples and 2.0 ms⁻¹ for F3S.20S-T6 samples.

PM AA6061-T6 / 90°

a)

PM AA6061-T6 / 45°

b)

PM AA6061-30 vol.%SiCp-T6 / 90°

c)

PM AA6061-30 vol.%SiCp-T6 / 45°

d)

Figure 4. SEM micrographs of PM AA6061-T6 (a and b) and PM AA6061-30 vol.%SiCp-T6 (c and d) samples after the 100 h erosion tests at 150 °C on the surfaces with impact angles of 90° (a and c) and 45° (b and d). The impact velocity was 2.0 ms⁻¹.

For the cast composites the T6-heat treatment and the increasing of the SiCp content from 10 to 20 vol.% evidently had stronger effect on improving the hardness than decreasing the ductility leading to better erosion resistance. The ductility of the cast alloys is inherently low and the reinforcement additions and T6 treatment do not the ductility significantly.

The effect of the reinforcement particulates should be in acting as barriers against the erosive action of the erodent grains on the composite. If the reinforcements are large enough and the bonding between the matrix alloy is strong, they would be expected to remain anchored on the surface for a longer time until they get broken down into smaller particulates or until the matrix alloy no longer can support them.

In the case of the tested materials the size of the reinforcements could have been too small compared with the size of erosive particles, to provide effective resistance to erosion [1]. The bonding has been strong enough to prevent the loosening of the reinforcements.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In the fluidised bed erosion tests the volume loss and the erosion rate of the wrought PM AA6061 alloy, AA6061/SiCp and AA6061/Al₂O₃p composites were clearly smaller as compared to those of the cast AlSiMg alloy and AlSiMg/SiCp composites.

The reinforcement addition did not have a significant influence on the volume loss and the wear rate of the hot extruded and upsetted PM alloys. Also the variation of the reinforcement size had no effect on the erosion resistance.

The Al₂O₃p reinforced AA6061 alloys had a slightly smaller volume loss and erosion rate compared to those of the corresponding SiCp reinforced alloys.

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